

Diagnosis Report for Gradient-Based Optimization of a Dynamical System

An Appendix of “Expectation-Maximization Style Algorithm for Task-Driven Differentiable Renderer Optimization”

1. Problem setup

1) System definition

The system is set to back propagate a loss (defined on v) through the intact structure of a time-unrolled stepping algorithm of the Gray-Scott model, each step following:

$$u_{next} = u + D_u \Delta u - uv^2 + F(1 - u)$$

$$v_{next} = v + D_v \Delta v + uv^2 - (F + k) v$$

We use this backpropagation-based optimization to fit D_u , D_v , F , and k for the distribution of a batch of 512 similar target patterns sized 128 x 128.

Backpropagation is done through all unrolled steps. We coded a truncated backpropagation version but disabled (commented) it, as computational resource was still sufficient, and no gradient explosion/vanishing was observed.

2) Boundary and initial conditions

For the stepping algorithm, we use the periodic boundary condition. Initial conditions are generated randomly for each training step, but following a controlled pattern:

$$u_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 0.50, & \text{if } 54 \leq i \leq 74 \text{ and } 54 \leq j \leq 74 \\ \text{clamp}((1.0 + e_{i,j}), [0.0, 1.5]), & e_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1), \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$
$$v_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 0.25, & \text{if } 54 \leq i \leq 74 \text{ and } 54 \leq j \leq 74 \\ \text{clamp}(e_{i,j}, [0.0, 1.0]), & e_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{N}(0,1), \text{ otherwise} \end{cases}$$

3) Target patterns

Target patterns are generated by time stepping using $D_u=0.16$, $D_v=0.08$, $F=0.035$, $k=0.065$ until no pixel differs from the last step more than $1e-4$ or until we reach the maximum step 40000.

4) Optimization objective

We calculated the 2D power spectrum of the generated pattern and a sampled target pattern using

$$S = \log(\text{fftshift}(|\mathcal{F}(\tilde{x})|^2 + \epsilon) \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times W}$$

, where

$$\tilde{x} = x - \frac{1}{HW} \sum_{i,j} x_{i,j}$$

. Then, we use L2 loss between S_{target} and $S_{generated}$.

We also used an updated “windowed” 2D power spectrum, which calculates exactly the same thing in each of the 64 16x16 windows of the 128x128 image. The same L2 loss was then applied between target and generated patterns.

2. Experimental setup

- 1) We completely avoid NaN, Inf, and non-[0,1] values of v , using an adaptive learning rate mechanism.
- 2) Restricted ranges of parameters Du, Dv, F, k , by setting them as $softplus(\log_Du)$, $softplus(\log_Dv)$, $0.1sigmoid(raw_k)$, $0.1sigmoid(raw_F)$, adding another layer of parameters $\log_Du, \log_Dv, raw_k, raw_F$ at the bottom of the network.
- 3) The empirical range of Du and Dv satisfies CFL criterion for 2-dimensional problems: $D\Delta t(\frac{1}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{1}{\Delta y^2}) \leq \frac{1}{2}$. With $\Delta x = 1.0, \Delta y = 1.0, \Delta t = 1.0$, this means $D \leq \frac{1}{4}$ in most cases, although we did not take dedicated measures to strictly ensure it.

3. Training and results

The generation mechanism of initial states in Section 1.2 (with limited randomness) is shared between target and training.

Where to stop training had to be decided manually, because loss value almost constantly remained between 245.0~270.0. In very rare cases, a few losses along the way jump to lower than 20.0 and jump back. In later manual checks, the patterns generated at loss values 10.0~20.0 do not match actual target patterns (compare the fourth and the seventh images in Fig. 1(a) and their corresponding vertical positions of dots in Fig.1(b)), but similar manual check also shows that target-matching steady-state patterns happen at a location with an even lower loss (<10.0) (compare the fourth and the third images in Fig.1(a) and their corresponding vertical positions of dots in Fig.1(b)). Gradients didn't lead the optimizer toward the low loss values; instead, we arrived at 10.0~20.0 by chance and pass by without stopping (or, in the case where loss<10.0, we cut off the training right at that iteration, only knowing it was close to targets during later manual checking).

We updated our loss function to windowed 2d power spectrum, observing that low loss values (<20.0) were assigned to non-target patterns. This loss is described in Section 1.4 and ensures that the dominant Fourier frequencies do not only come from a part of the full 128x128. Under the new loss function, we observed similar fluctuations of loss values with

no converging trend, this time around 230. In both windowed and non-windowed cases, small parameter updates already require hundreds of iterations to allow any meaningful change. Also, further check of the windowed loss version wasn't doing better, if not worse (compare the left and right of Fig. 1(b)).

(a) Stead-state patterns

(b) Corresponding losses. Left: 2d power spectrum loss; right: windowed 2d power spectrum loss
Figure 1

As we mentioned, one trajectory achieved a set of parameters close to target (the one with $loss < 10.0$), but the learning rate adjustment point and stopping point are picked out through manually animating pattern generations at random checkpoints and comparing with targets. The algorithm itself has no clue from the training output to decide this trajectory. That the loss values fluctuate without convergence is an illustration to this lacking. We still record this trajectory as the following:

- Initial parameters $D_u=0.1270$, $D_v=0.1269$, $F=0.0500$, $k=0.0501$.
- Initial training: used L2 loss on 2d power spectrum, learning rate $1.2e-2$, and trained for 8918 iterations, arrived at $D_u=0.1285$, $D_v=0.0734$, $F=0.0429$, $k=0.0682$.
- Continued training using L2 loss on 2d power spectrum and learning rate $1e-3$, for 98 iterations, arrived at $D_u=0.1343$, $D_v=0.0679$, $F=0.0429$, $k=0.0653$.

We have one file showing simultaneous animations of four pattern evolutions, under: 1) initial parameters, 2) parameters after initial 8918 iterations, 3) parameters after an extra 98 iterations, and 4) target parameters. The four evolutions are arranged from left to right in the file: https://github.com/Yan-Yang-bot/bp2renderer/blob/main/media/gray_scott.gif.

4. Further probing the loss landscapes

To further understand the shapes of the loss landscapes, we plotted some cross-sections of the landscape.

The first batch of these cross-sections are along single parameters, each of k , F , D_u , and D_v shown in one of the four plots (Fig. 2). Along each of the four parameter variation lines, we also have a chain of simultaneous animations:

- Along k : https://github.com/Yan-Yang-bot/bp2renderer/blob/main/media/animate_loss_landscape_k_0.055-0.066_uniform.mp4
- Along F : [https://github.com/Yan-Yang-bot/bp2renderer/blob/main/media/animate_loss_landscape_F_0.30-\(5\)-0.50-\(2\)-0.54-\(1\)-0.59.mp4](https://github.com/Yan-Yang-bot/bp2renderer/blob/main/media/animate_loss_landscape_F_0.30-(5)-0.50-(2)-0.54-(1)-0.59.mp4)
- Along D_u : https://github.com/Yan-Yang-bot/bp2renderer/blob/main/media/animate_loss_landscape_Du_0.15-0.25_uniform.mp4
- Along D_v : https://github.com/Yan-Yang-bot/bp2renderer/blob/main/media/animate_loss_landscape_Dv_0.03134-0.083_uniform.mp4

The second batch of these cross-sections are 2-dimensional, showing loss values on 2-dimensional plains formed by varying two parameters together. In Fig. 3, we show two of such 2-dimensional plains, one for F - D_v with coarser granularity of 10×10 datapoints, the other for F - k with finer granularity of 50×50 datapoints. We also have the generated patterns arranged in a matrix correspondent to the F - k loss value plot shown in Fig. 4.

The figures and animations helped to reveal our issues: loss value cliffs, likely corresponding to bifurcations in the parameter space, exist on the cross-section along each parameter and also on those for parameter pairs. The high loss sides of cliffs

correspond to all-1 or all-0 solutions. These cliffs divide uniform steady-state regions and pattern-forming regions, and our gradient-based optimizer had been mostly navigating on the former, only very occasionally and briefly passing by the latter, which was how the almost-uniform loss values happened.

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4